

TREvolution Interim Report

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Introduction

This interim report documents work undertaken to explore compatibility between Vantage6 and the Five Safes TES based on the GA4GH TES (Task Execution Service) API.

The objectives were to:

- Understand how the Five Safes TES represents work and executes workloads
- Identify where the TES API can act as an interoperability layer, and where it cannot
- Experiment with practical integration approaches
- Evaluate short-term and long-term integration options
- Create small technical demonstrations to experiment with integration options and further understanding of the TES API and the Five Safes TES execution model

This report summarizes the architectural comparison, experiments performed, integration options considered, and key design decisions required for interoperability.

Overview of Components

Vantage6

Vantage6 is an orchestration system for federated analytics. It offers a developer-friendly model (algorithms packaged as containers, tasks targeting organizations) and a runtime model (nodes execute tasks and report results to the server).

Key components

- **Server:** Coordination layer for tasks and results.
- **Node:** Executes the containerized algorithms at each participating organization.
- **Algorithm:** Container images executed against local datasets.
- **Aggregator node:** In aggregation-based algorithms, one node may act as an "aggregator" node to coordinate a multi-step workflow and combine partial results.

Entities

- **Project:** When multiple centers (e.g. hospitals) collaborate on a research project using Vantage6, we call this a project. A project contains multiple collaborations and is hosted on a dedicated Vantage6 server.
- **Organization:** Owns data and deploys nodes to participate in collaborations.
- **Collaboration:** A group of organizations working toward a shared goal over a defined set of datasets. Organizations join by registering nodes with their dataset(s) attached.
- **Dataset:** Each organization keeps control of its datasets, which are used by the algorithms spawned by their nodes for computations.
- **Task:** A computation request sent by a researcher (or aggregator) to other nodes via the server. Internally, one task usually becomes one run per target organization.
- **Result:** Algorithms return privacy-preserving results to the server, which makes them available to researchers or aggregator nodes.
- **User:** Interact via the Vantage6 client, web UI, or API to submit tasks, retrieve results, and manage nodes.

Workflow

- 1) Researcher uses the Python client library (or the API/UI) to create a new task with:
 - an algorithm image
 - a list of target organizations
 - an input payload
 - optional dataset labels
- 2) The Vantage6 client encrypts the task input per target organization
- 3) The server validates permissions, stores the task, and creates a run per target organization
- 4) Nodes receive a WebSocket signal and/or poll for open runs
- 5) Each node starts algorithm containers locally:
 - it writes input/output/token files
 - it injects environment variables (including dataset URIs)
- 6) The algorithm runs and writes output
- 7) The node patches the run result back to the server. If end-to-end encryption is enabled, the node encrypts the result for the initiating organization before sending it.

Two details are important for interoperability:

- Vantage6 does not utilize a common external execution standard. The task/run API and node-side runtime contract are Vantage6 specific.

- Many Vantage6 algorithms rely on a wrapper contract. Input file, output file, and database URI environment variables are central to algorithm image behavior.

Trust and policy

In Vantage6, a node is typically responsible for deciding which algorithm images it will run. Typical controls include:

- node authentication to the server (API keys)
- an allowlist for algorithm images and/or algorithm stores (commonly a regex; can be combined with digest pinning depending on deployment)
- optional "always pull" behavior to avoid using stale local images
- end-to-end encryption of inputs and results:
 - o the server stores ciphertext
 - o nodes decrypt their inputs
 - o nodes encrypt results for the initiating organization, which can then decrypt (researcher or an aggregator node in that organization)

Any interoperability approach needs to respect these node-side policy controls, even if execution is delegated to an external runtime.

Five Safes TES

The Five Safes TES exposes a TES-compatible ingress API to researchers and provides a multi-stage pipeline that includes governance controls (project membership, TRE selection, approvals) and explicit egress workflow. Various aspects of the service relevant to integrations with the Vantage6 platform are outlined below.

The role of TES in the Five Safes TES

The Five Safes TES uses the GA4GH TES API task execution schemas for its tasks and the submission interface:

- A researcher submits a TES task document to the submission interface
- The system stores the TES object
- A TRE agent later fetches that task and forwards it to TES executor (in this case, Funnel was used).
 - o Some transformation of the TES task takes place between the TRE Agent and Funnel, so that the right "local" (node) paths are present.

TES is used as the "unit of execution", but additional federation concepts that TES does not standardize (target "project" and target TREs/nodes) are required. Currently, these are supplied using a *tags* section in the TES task.

Workflow

In the Five Safes TES, Inputs and outputs are not embedded in the task. Instead, object references are materialized through an S3-compatible storage.

- The researcher uploads input objects (task parameters for an algorithm, not datasets) to a submission-layer-side bucket.
- The TRE agent copies those objects into a TRE-side MinIO bucket, rewrites the TES input URLs to point to that TRE-side bucket, and forwards the transformed TES task to the TES executor. The TES executor (Funnel in our demo) then mounts those inputs into the algorithm container for execution.
- After egress approval, approved outputs are copied back to a submission-side bucket for researcher visibility.

Mandatory inputs (datasets) are injected by the TRE agent

In our demo setup, the TRE agent injects a configured "mandatory input" into the TES task before execution. This is used to mount local datasets into the container-runtime.

We've considered adding a directory for mandatory input, which might provide a simple-enough, multi-dataset mechanism that maps reasonably well to Vantage6's "database labels" concept. It is not presented as a final proposal here – just a potential short-term solution.

Egress is a first-class stage

The end-to-end lifecycle includes an explicit egress review stage.

- execution output is produced into TRE-side object storage
- an egress request is created listing output objects
- an operator (human) approves or rejects files
- only approved outputs are copied back to a submission-side bucket for researcher visibility

This stage has some implications when mapping Vantage6 semantics: Vantage6 typically considers a run "complete" when the node has produced results, whereas in DARE the "researcher-visible completion" may only occur after egress review.

Equivalences And Major Differences

The two systems solve similar problems but with some different primitives. Understanding the mapping helps decide where to integrate.

Rough equivalences

- Vantage6 server is most similar to the submission layer in that it coordinates tasks and results. Due to algorithm controls (allowed algorithms list) present in vantage6 nodes, nodes can choose to place less trust on the server compared to the equivalent submission layer.
- Vantage6 node is most similar to the TRE agent plus TES executor runtime in the Five Safes TES (and rest of TRE-side components like Camunda, MinIO, etc.). In native Vantage6, the node both orchestrates and executes a local algorithm run / task. In the Five Safes TES, orchestration (transfer/polling/rewrites) happens in the TRE agent, while execution is delegated to a TES executor (such as Funnel). A key design difference is that the Five Safes TES uses a standard execution schema/interface for this handoff (TES).
- Vantage6 "database labels" are closest to the Five Safes TES idea of mounting datasets into the runtime. In Vantage6, the researcher can specify which "databases" to use by label in the task, and the node resolves those labels to local datasets. In the Five Safes TES, datasets may be made available via mechanisms such as mandatory inputs. A key compatibility question is how to represent "use dataset X" in a way that is natural for researchers but still maps to TRE-local dataset availability and policy.

Major differences that affect compatibility

Protocol and schema

- Vantage6 uses its own task/run schema and WebSocket signaling.
- The Five Safes TES uses TES for execution, extending it with tags and APIs.

Auth and trust boundary

- The TRE agent trusts the submission layer for "what to execute". Vantage6 node has optional allowlists for algorithms.
- Many Vantage6 algorithms use the official wrapper which allows researchers to target which of the python functions they'd like to serve as the entry point. In the 5 Safes TES, the researcher can modify the CMD entry point of the container.
- TRE has an egress control step, whereas Vantage6 nodes do not.

Data movement

- Vantage6 typically mounts host paths into algorithm containers and

injects env vars pointing to those mount paths.

- The Five Safes TES materializes objects into a work directory managed by the TES

executor (Funnel), based on (for example) S3 URLs and TES fields

Iteration and orchestration

- Many Vantage6 algorithms are iterative and use *AlgorithmClient* calls from inside containers to create new tasks or exchange intermediate results.

- TES seems more fundamentally "one task = one container execution". Iteration must be modeled externally (multiple TES tasks).

Possible Integrations

Due to some of the similarities in both use-cases and high-level architecture, as well as the flexibility of the TES API approach, a plethora of different TES-Vantage6 integrations can be considered.

A TES relay mode in the Vantage6 node

One approach we experimented with is a TES relay mode in the Vantage6 node. Conceptually, this replaces local container execution in a vantage6 node with:

- upload of Vantage6 run input (algorithm parameters) to the Five Safes TES submission-side object storage
- creation of a TES task pointing at the original Vantage6 algorithm image (created at the submission layer)
- polling the submission layer for TES completion state
- patching Vantage6 run status to the vantage6 server with a result payload

To make existing Vantage6 algorithm images runnable in TES, this approach creates TES executor environment variables that mimic Vantage6's wrapper contract. Input and output files point to the TES materialized paths, and dataset labels are mapped to paths inside the container runtime via a node config mapping (for example: *olympic_athletes*-> */datasets/olympic_athletes.csv*).

Because environment values are encoded identically to Vantage6, Vantage6's wrappers can decode them identically. This is the core mechanism that makes existing Vantage6 algorithms portable to the Five Safes TES execution runtime without rewriting the algorithm image.

However, this is a customized/contrived approach. A less custom direction could be for the algorithm itself (running inside the container) to read a TES-like task description so it can understand I/O paths and parameters in a more explicit and portable way.

This relay mode is explicitly limited as it would only support non-aggregator Vantage6 tasks that do not require *AlgorithmClient* round-trips from inside the algorithm container. *AlgorithmClient* is the object used in vantage6 for a node to communicate to the server and send sub-tasks.

Adopt TES API in Vantage6 server and node

Foregoing the integration with the 5 Safes TES weave, another option is the integration of TES in all Vantage6 components, such that both the Vantage6 server and nodes can represent and execute work via TES (in addition to the existing API).

Pros

- a clean long-term interoperability story
- potential for shared tooling and shared algorithm portability

Cons

- large scope: Vantage6's task/run model, encryption model, and collaboration semantics do not map 1:1 to TES
- TES does not standardize core federation concepts Vantage6 relies on (node selection, aggregator selection, dataset selection, and multi-step iterative workflows)

Assessment

This is best treated as a longer-term convergence topic, not the fastest path to a working integration.

A gateway/middle-layer between Vantage6 and DARE/TRE

To keep changes to both platforms to a minimum, another option is to introduce an adapter that translates Vantage6 tasks into TES submissions and manages the data-path mappings and status mappings. This approach would keep the Five Safes TES-specific auth/routing logic in one place.

Pros

- smallest disruption to both ecosystems
- incremental delivery: start with "local" Vantage6 algorithms first

- easy to validate using the existing demo stack
- avoids forcing either side to adopt the other's status/governance model (maybe)

Cons

- adapter complexity can grow unless the contract is made explicit
- only supports a subset of Vantage6 algorithms
- single-shot computations are feasible, but algorithms requiring the *AlgorithmClient* or aggregation need additional design
- status/result mapping must be designed carefully (especially around egress)
- this would be a custom integration. A more ideal scenario is for both platforms to converge on a standard (or set of standards) and achieve broader interoperability that way.

Assessment

This is the most pragmatic near-term option and the one we have been experimenting with (for example, via a TES relay concept in the node).

Mimic submission API behavior in the Vantage6 server

Extend the Vantage6 server so a TRE agent can poll it and retrieve work using the same interface it expects from the Submission API.

Pros

- reuses TRE agent behavior with minimal change
- centers using TRE agent already wouldn't need to install a Vantage6 node

Cons

- requires reproducing an API compatibility surface in Vantage6 server (projects, TRE routing, bucket handling, status model), which may not fit Vantage6 well

- creates a long-term maintenance obligation: "keep Vantage6 server in sync with Five Safes TES submission contracts"
- might require changes to the Five Safes TES to avoid disconnecting an existing TRE agent from its original submission layer

Assessment

Feasible, but does not align well with TRevolution's goals.

Design Topics That Need Explicit Decisions

These topics show up during translation work. Making them explicit early might help keep the integration from becoming "glue code".

TES tags are carrying non-TES concepts

The five Safes TES uses the TES *tags* field to carry routing and governance context. For example, *project* and *tres* are not TES concepts, but are required inputs to the Five Safes TES system. If Vantage6 is to target TES, when targeting the Five Safes TES, we need a stable convention for encoding these concepts (tags, headers, or a separate API) on top of TES.

TES does not fully covert the federated learning story

TES represents one unit of execution. It does not include a standard way to target a specific node, aggregator, or organization. There are also no standard execution constraints. Vantage6 algorithms, for example, do not have access to the internet by default. Lastly, no standard is defined yet for dataset selection or dataset information exchange.

Any non-trivial federated learning workflow will therefore need additional protocol(s) on top of TES. The Five Safes TES currently addresses parts of this via its submission model and TRE agent routing, and vantage6 does so using its own APIs/tools.

Egress review cannot validate privacy by itself

Egress review is a powerful governance control, but it does not guarantee that outputs are privacy-preserving in a strict sense. For example, an algorithm may output summary statistics such as mean/median. An egress reviewer may not be able to tell whether a statistic was computed over many rows (intended) or is effectively revealing one individual's value (problematic), especially if the algorithm is malicious or contains bugs.

Interoperability does not remove the need for algorithm governance: allowlists, code review, DP techniques, or restricted analysis templates remain important.

Egress review can get impractical for iterative algorithms

Some algorithms (e.g. logistic regression, training neural nets, etc.) might require many iterations to converge to an acceptable solution. A human needing to approve every local output from every iteration could slow down the process. Moreover, due to the number of approvals necessary, approval without proper review becomes likely, defeating the purpose of the egress control. Thought should therefore be put into how to balance the extra assurance that egress control brings, and the convenience of fast and automated iterations.

Status mapping across systems

The integration involves at least four independent state machines:

- Vantage6 run state
- TES task state (QUEUED/RUNNING/COMPLETE/ERROR)
- Five Safes TES submission child state (transfer, running, complete, etc)
- Five Safes TES egress stage

A precise definition of “completion” is required from the Vantage6 researcher perspective. Two interpretations are possible:

- Completion on TES `COMPLETE` (execution done, but egress pending)
- Completion on egress approval (researcher-visible completion)

Exposing intermediate states (e.g., “egress pending”) within Vantage6 would improve transparency but is not required for baseline interoperability.

Further Work

We will further explore the aforementioned integration options and continue the integration experiments. At the moment, implementing a TES relay mode in the Vantage6 node seems like the most promising avenue to pursue.

In parallel, we will consider what else it would take to support a more complete federated learning / federated analytics story from a standards perspective. While TES is an important step in the right direction, more standardization is required.